

Self-Efficacy of Secondary School Teachers In Relation To Their Gender and Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

Teacher self-efficacy refers to teachers' belief in their ability to produce expected student outcomes. This belief has a powerful impact on students because it allows teachers to motivate even the most academically challenged students. Hence, the present investigation was carried out to study the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender and job satisfaction. Descriptive Survey method of research was used for this study. A sample of 750 secondary school teachers was selected by employing incidental sampling technique. Data were collected by using standardized research tools i.e. Teacher's Self-Efficacy Scale by Sood and Sen and Teacher's Job Satisfaction Scale by Y. Mudgil, I.S. Muhar and P. Bhatia. Descriptive statistics and Analysis of variance were used to analyze the data. There was no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender. Secondary school teachers with different level of job satisfaction differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. Gender and job satisfaction taken together have no significant interactional effect on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Gender, Job Satisfaction.

Introduction

Teacher efficacy, as a belief, is expected to guide teachers' behaviour decisions and motivation in the classroom. As a belief, teacher efficacy is expected to guide teachers' behaviour decisions and motivation in the classroom. Teachers must not only be psychologically and physically comfortable in order to teach effectively, but they must also believe that they can make a difference in the lives of the children whom they are teaching and those who are learning. They must believe that their professional work is making a difference in the lives of their students. Teacher efficacy for teaching, in particular, influences their daily teaching decisions and willingness to employ specific strategies and techniques. Self-efficacy has a significant impact on how people think, feel, act, and motivate themselves. A higher sense of self-efficacy leads people to view difficult situations as tasks to be completed rather than dangers to be avoided. They create tough goals and show a deeper sense of dedication to them, as well as higher intrinsic interest and attention in their work. Job is a vital component of human activity. A job is an effective way to satisfy many kinds of demands, including those for ego, security, and social requirements. The concept of 'job-satisfaction' has come from Industrial Psychology and it is now one of very extensively explored aspect of human efficiency at work. When there is satisfaction in job, work is done with great care and sincerity. Job-satisfaction is the whole matrix of job factors that make a person like work situation and be willing to lead for it without distaste at the beginning of this work day. Job satisfaction essentially implies one of the most

pleasant and keenly sought-after state of mind. It can be made a vehicle for the achievement of a higher end. High quality teaching staff is the foundation of any effective educational system. Since regular interactions between teachers and students are the core of the educational process, finding and keeping excellent teachers is the most important requirement for education. Understanding the elements that contribute to teaching quality is crucial for the development of high quality. One of these elements is job satisfaction, which has received extensive study from organizational scholars and has been connected to both organizational commitment and performance. Job satisfaction requires taking into consideration variables like pay, supervision, stability of employment situation, prospects for progress, aspiration level of employers, and social position. It is the degree of agreement between one's expectations and their rewards. It directly affects how well an employee performs. An employee's attitude toward the workplace will be positive if they are properly compensated, given improved opportunities for advancement, given good working circumstances, and requested to work in a friendly setting. This optimistic outlook will result in improved performance and increased output in both quality and quantity. **Singh and Katlana (2015)** revealed from the study that mean score of self-efficacy of male teachers of universities (3.72) was less than self-efficacy of female teachers of universities (4.16) Hence it was concluded that self-efficacy of female teachers were higher than male teachers.

Kent and Giles (2017) revealed from the responses of the participants that 91% of participants incorporated technology, whereas 95% of participants reported confident in their ability to utilize technology in teaching. It was further revealed that 90% of participants had confidence of incorporating technology in their curriculum.

Soto and Rojas (2019) inferred from the study that teacher self-efficacy job satisfaction, promoter citizenship behaviour, and organizational citizenship behaviour were positively and significantly related to each other.

Demir (2020) concluded from the study that self-efficacy beliefs had a positive effect on teachers 'motivation, organizational commitment, job satisfaction and job involvement. Further, the study showed that there was a positive relation between self-efficacy and organizational commitment whereas job satisfaction had direct and indirect impact on job involvement.

Hasan and Ibourk (2021) found a positive correlation between self-efficacy and job satisfaction whereas both dimensions of teacher burnout (emotional exhaustion and depersonalization) were negatively related to job satisfaction.

Medaille et al. (2022) concluded from the study that sense of confidence varied throughout thesis process, several factors was identified which intervened self-efficacy of students.

It has been observed on the basis of the thorough review of the literature that very few studies are on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction. Hence, it was decided to see the impact of gender and job satisfaction on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the gender-wise difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.
2. To study the difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their level of job satisfaction.
3. To study the interactional effect of gender and job satisfaction on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender.
2. There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their level of job satisfaction.
3. There exists no significant interaction between gender and job satisfaction with respect to self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

Methodology

In the present investigation, descriptive method of research was used to achieve the objectives of the study.

Sampling

A representative sample of 750 secondary school teachers were selected from schools of Shimla, Solan and Sirmour districts of Himachal Pradesh by employing incidental sampling technique.

Research Tools Used

In the present study, following research tools were used:

1. Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale by Sood and Sen (2017)
2. Teacher's Job Satisfaction Scale by Y. Mudgil, I.S. Muhar and P. Bhatia (2012).

Analysis of Data

For analysis and interpretation of data, descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used, details of which is given below:

In order to study the main and interactional effects of gender and level of job satisfaction on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, Analysis of Variance (2x3 factor design) having two types of gender i.e. male and female and three levels of job satisfaction i.e. high, moderate and low, was applied on the mean scores of self-efficacy of secondary school teachers. The means and standard deviations of self-efficacy scores with respect to gender and level of job satisfaction are given in Table 1.

Table 1:
Means And Standard Deviations Of Self Efficacy Scores With Regard To Gender And Job Satisfaction

Sr. No.	Level of Job Satisfaction (B) Gender (A)		Mean Self-Efficacy Scores			
			High Level	Moderate Level	Low Level	Total
I	Male	Mean	235.50	227.93	225.35	228.76
		S.D.	37.359	35.359	23.855	34.649
		N	64	325	48	437
II	Female	Mean	236.14	237.39	220.16	234.80
		S.D.	31.299	28.040	23.969	28.521
		N	43	226	44	313
III	Total	Mean	235.76	231.81	222.87	231.28
		S.D.	34.897	32.862	23.921	32.352
		N	107	551	92	750

From the mean scores of self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with regard to gender and job

satisfaction, F-values were calculated. The results are given in the Table 2 as follows:

Table 2
Summary Of The Results Of Analysis Of Variance For Self-Efficacy Of Secondary School Teachers With Respect To Gender And Job Satisfaction

Sr. No.	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares (Variance)	F-Ratio
I	Gender (A)	268.415	1	268.415	0.262 ^{NS}
II	Job Satisfaction (B)	9567.309	2	4783.655	4.667*
III	Interaction (AxB)	5195.26	2	2597.63	2.534 ^{NS}
IV	Error Variance	762533.56	744	1024.911	
V	Total	783924.759	749		

NS-Non Significant

* Even at 0.05 level of significance

(i) Main Effects

(a) Gender (A)

The calculated value of 'F-Ratio' for the main effect of gender on the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, for a degree of freedom 1 and 744, was found to be 0.262 which is below the F-table value 3.85 even at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis no. 1 that, "There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender" was

retained. Thus, it is interpreted that there is no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender. However, on the basis of mean values, it is clear that female secondary school teachers possessed high level of self-efficacy (Mean-234.8) as compared to male secondary school teachers (Mean-228.76). The mean self-efficacy scores of male and female secondary school teachers were shown in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1
Mean Self-Efficacy Scores Of Male And Female Secondary School Teachers

(B) JOB SATISFACTION (B)

The calculated value of 'F' for finding the main effect of job satisfaction on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, for degrees of freedom 2 and 744, came out to be 4.667 which is greater than the F-table value 4.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis no. 2 that, "There exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary

school teachers with respect to their level of job satisfaction," was not retained. Hence, it can be concluded that secondary school teachers with different level of job satisfaction differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. The Figure 2 shows the mean self-efficacy scores of secondary school teachers with respect to level of job satisfaction.

Figure 2
Mean Self-Efficacy Scores Of Secondary School Teachers With Different Level Of Job Satisfaction

In order to locate the significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with regard to different level of job satisfaction, statistical technique 't' test was applied, details of which are given below:

(i) Self-Efficacy of Secondary School Teachers with respect to High Job Satisfaction and Moderate Job Satisfaction

Satisfaction and Moderate Job Satisfaction

Table 3 shows the value of means, standard deviations, standard error of difference between means and t-value.

TABLE 3

't' value showing the significance of difference in mean self-efficacy scores of secondary school teachers in relation to High and Moderate level of Job Satisfaction

Sr.No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	SED	t-Value
1	High Job Satisfaction	107	235.76	34.897	656	3.51	1.124 ^{NS}
2	Moderate Job Satisfaction	551	231.81	32.862			

NS-Non Significant

The observed value of 't' for testing the significant difference in mean self-efficacy scores of secondary school teachers with high job satisfaction and secondary school teachers having moderate level of job satisfaction, came out to be 1.124 which is not significant even at 0.05 level of significance, for df 656. It means that there exists no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers having high and moderate level of change proneness. However, on the basis of mean values,

secondary school teachers with high job satisfaction possessed high self-efficacy as compared to teachers with moderate level of job satisfaction.

(ii) Self-Efficacy of Secondary School Teachers with respect to High Job Satisfaction and Low Job Satisfaction

Table 4 shows the value of means, standard deviations, standard error of difference between means and t- value.

TABLE 4

't' Value Showing the Significance of Difference in Mean Self-Efficacy Scores of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to High and Moderate level of Job Satisfaction

Sr.No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	SED	t-Value
1	High Job Satisfaction	107	235.76	34.897	197	4.31	2.989**
2	Low Job Satisfaction	92	222.87	23.921			

****Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance.**

Table 4 shows the computed 't' value for finding the significance of difference in the mean self-efficacy scores of secondary school teachers having high level of job satisfaction and low level of job satisfaction, which is 2.989. This value is significant at 0.01 level of significance, for df 197. Hence, it may be said that there exists a significant difference in the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with high and low level of job satisfaction. Further, secondary school teachers having high level

of job satisfaction (Mean-235.76) possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction (mean-222.87).

(iii) Self-Efficacy of Secondary School Teachers with respect to Moderate Job Satisfaction and Low Job Satisfaction

The value of means, standard deviations, standard error of difference between means and t- value are given in Table 5 as follows:

TABLE 5
't' Value Showing the Significance of Difference in Mean Self-Efficacy Scores of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Moderate and Low level of Job Satisfaction

Sr.No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	SD	df	SED	t-Value
1	Moderate Job Satisfaction	551	231.81	32.862	641	3.58	2.501**
2	Low Job Satisfaction	92	222.87	23.921			

****Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance.**

The calculated value of 't' for testing the significance of mean scores of self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with moderate level of job satisfaction and secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction, came out to be 2.501 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance, for df 641. Hence, it may be said that secondary school teachers having moderate level of job satisfaction differed significantly from secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction with respect to their self-efficacy. Further, from the mean scores, it is clear that secondary school teachers having moderate level of job satisfaction (231.81) possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction (222.87).

(ii) Interactional Effect (AXB)

The obtained value of 'F' for the interactional effect of gender and job satisfaction on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers, came out to be 2.534 for a degree of freedom 2 and 744 . This value is below the F-table value 4.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the Hypothesis no. 3 that, "There exists no significant interaction between gender and job satisfaction with respect to self-efficacy of secondary school teachers" was retained. Therefore, it may be interpreted that the gender and job satisfaction taken together have no significant interactional effect on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

Conclusions:

1. There was no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender. However, on the basis of mean values, it is clear that female secondary school teachers possessed high level of self-efficacy (Mean-234.80) as compared to male secondary school teachers (Mean-228.76).

2. Secondary school teachers with different level of job satisfaction differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. There existed no significant difference in self-efficacy of secondary school teachers having high and moderate level of change proneness. However, on the basis of mean values, secondary school teachers with high job satisfaction possessed high self-efficacy as compared to teachers with moderate level of job satisfaction. Secondary School teachers having high level of job satisfaction (Mean-235.76) possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction (mean-222.87). Secondary school teachers having moderate level of job satisfaction differed significantly from secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction with respect to their self-efficacy. Further, from the mean scores, it is clear that secondary school teachers having moderate level of job satisfaction (231.81) possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction (222.87).
3. There existed no significant interaction between gender and job satisfaction with respect to self-efficacy of secondary school teachers. Therefore, it may be interpreted that the gender and job satisfaction taken together have no significant interactional effect on self-efficacy of secondary school teachers.

Implications:

The present research was done to investigate the self-efficacy of secondary school teachers in relation to their gender and job satisfaction. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in self-efficacy

of secondary school teachers with respect to their gender. However, on the basis of mean values, it is clear that female secondary school teachers possessed high level of self-efficacy as compared to male secondary school teachers. Hence, there is a great need to increase the self-efficacy of both gender especially male secondary school teachers. It was further revealed that Secondary school teachers with different level of job satisfaction differed significantly from each other with regard to their self-efficacy. Secondary School teachers having high level of job satisfaction possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction. Further, it was found that secondary school teachers shaving moderate level of job satisfaction possessed high self-efficacy as compared to secondary school teachers having low level of job satisfaction. Unless a teacher is satisfied with his/her job, he/she cannot deliver his/her best and he/she will be a loss not to himself/herself only but also to the whole education system. For improving the level of job satisfaction in teachers; principals, school management and head of institutions should provide them with creative and meaningful tasks because repetitive routine work often leads to dissatisfaction to the job. Highly qualified teachers at low grade posts feel job dissatisfaction, so performance based promotion avenues should be made available for the teachers. There should be regular exchange of teachers working in rural and urban schools. The teacher should be provided opportunity to self-pace themselves. The frequent and non-critical feedback of teacher can improve their level of job satisfaction. Social security and special allowances should be provided. Activities such as celebration of teacher's day, cultural events etc. can enhance their level of job satisfaction and professional commitment which ultimately affect their self-efficacy significantly.

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